

Research Article

G-MediAlert: A Handy G6PD References for Pharmacy Personnel

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Abstract: *G-MediAlert is a mobile app prototype developed to address the safety concerns of individuals with glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, particularly in community pharmacy settings. This simple yet practical tool offers a curated list of medications categorized by risk levels: possible risk and definite risk. These classifications are intended to guide pharmacy personnel in making safer dispensing decisions in fast paced environments. Originally designed for use during locum shifts, G-MediAlert fills a real-world gap in current practice, where instant reference tools for G6PD-related drug risks are limited. Initial informal feedback indicated that this app is easy to navigate with users appreciating the quick search functionality. G-MediAlert demonstrates strong commercial potential due to its scalability, integration readiness, and ease of use. Future improvements may include expanding the medication database and incorporating a list of foods to avoid for these groups of patients. Ultimately, G-MediAlert aims to serve as a reliable support tool at pharmacy counters through accessible and user-friendly technology.*

Keywords: mobile application; g6pd deficiency; pharmacy education

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1. INTRODUCTION

Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) is a metabolism enzyme involved in the pentose phosphate pathway, which is crucial for red blood cell metabolism. A deficiency in G6PD enzyme can lead to hemolytic anemia following exposure to certain foods or medications (Li et al., 2020). G6PD deficiency is one of the most common genetic disorders, predominantly affecting population in Asia, the Middle East dan Africa. Globally, the number of reported of G6PD deficiency cases continues to rise, with India recording the highest prevalence (Liu et al., 2023). In Malaysia, the number of reported cases has shown a decreasing trend (Liu et al., 2023), although a prevalence of 15.2% has been reported among the Senoi Malaysia Orang Asli population (Koh et al., 2023). Individuals with G6PD deficiency are known to be at risk of hemolytic anemia, triggered by certain medications and foods. However, awareness and easy access to relevant medication information remain limited. Currently, drug information platforms such as UptoDate, Medscape or MIMS provide general drug information, but

they are not tailored for G6PD patients. This presents a challenge for community pharmacists, locum pharmacists and pharmacy assistants to identify the medication that should be avoided among G6PD customers quickly in fast-paced community pharmacy settings.

Previous studies and clinical guidelines have identified an extensive list of medications that are unsafe for G6PD-deficient customers due to the known risk (Gammal et al., 2023; Miyaoka et al., 2020). Unfortunately, access to this information is often fragmented, scattered across reference books or web searches. In practice, pharmacists often rely on Google searches, by typing for ‘medication to avoid in G6PD patients’ just to find the necessary answer, and this can be time consuming and inefficient. Mobile applications have been truly useful nowadays as they are easy to access with just one click, yet there’s almost no apps that are freely available focusing on this niche. Therefore, G-MediAlert addresses these gaps through a focused, simple and user-friendly design to support pharmacy personnel, especially locum pharmacists in efficiently identifying medications that may pose a risk to the G6PD-deficient customers.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The G-MediAlert mobile application prototype was developed using a no-code platform called Google AppSheet, which enables rapid deployment of mobile apps from structured data sources. Google AppSheet was chosen due to its cost effectiveness (Hassan et al., 2023), ease of access for all users and it requires no programming skills to develop and use the apps.

To design the apps, Google Sheets was used to store medication list and the risk classifications. A preliminary list of medications was entered into the sheets based on the MIMS Summary Table – Drugs to avoid in G6PD Deficiency. Each medication was categorized into two risks of classifications: definite and possible. Medications known to cause haemolytic reactions for G6PD deficient individuals were categorized as definite risk, while medications with a potential to trigger haemolytic reactions and required precautions use were classified as possible risk. The prototype includes several core features such a curated list of medication, a quick search button function and clear risk classification. Figure 1 to 3 shows a screenshot highlighting these features.

Figure 1: List of Medications

Figure 2: Clear risk classifications

Figure 3: Search quick functions

3. FINDINGS

Preliminary testing was conducted in a real-world community pharmacy setting during locum shift. The G-MediAlert app was used informally to assist pharmacy personnel in identifying medications with potential risk for G6PD deficient customers. Initial informal feedback gathered at a point of time from a small number of pharmacy personnel indicated that the app was user friendly and easy to navigate. The quick search functionality was particularly appreciated, as it reduces the time searching potential medication risk for their customers. The risk classification is clearly stated making it helpful and handy when handling prescription in fast paced environment like community pharmacy. Lastly, there is no technical issues reported during the early testing period.

Even without formal testing or large-scale implementation, early feedback suggest that G-MediAlert could fill a critical gap in medication safety for G6PD deficiency patient. This G-MediAlert app is not only be beneficial to pharmacy personnel, but it can also be used by patients and caretakers who choose to self-medicate using over the counter products or medications. Its simplicity and focused scope make it suitable for daily use in pharmacy settings, particularly at the busy counters of community pharmacies. As this is still a prototype design, future improvements should include formal feedback such as structured user surveys or semi structured interviews to validate its usability and effectiveness. Besides, expanding the current medication database and integrating a list of foods to avoid for patients with G6PD deficiency can be further explored for future development.

4. DISCUSSION

The use of mobile application in pharmacy settings offers numerous benefits. One of it, it enables pharmacy personnel to easily search medication-related information. This ease of access can eventually help improve medication adherence and reduce the adverse drug effect (Loria, 2023). For pharmacist, especially those working in fast paced working environments like community pharmacies, the ease of access to medication information at their fingertips can boost productivity and supports the efficient and timely delivery of pharmaceutical care to patients (Kho et al., 2022). The same goal applies to the development of G-MediAlert app, that is designed specifically to ease pharmacists' workflow during their shifts in community pharmacy settings. This apps offers a quick, user-friendly tools to identify medications that may pose a risk to G6PD-deficient customers. By reducing the need for time

consuming google search or reference books, this apps aims to streamline the dispensing process performed by pharmacists.

The design of mobile apps should embrace minimalism, aiming to keep the content in a clear and concise manner. A minimalism concept in design apps should emphasize simplicity, which helps prevent users from an overwhelming experience by excessive information (Durgekar et al., 2024). This design approach enhances usability by allowing users; whether pharmacist or patients to focus on the most important information without distraction, aligning well with the design for this mobile prototype.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, G-MediAlert is an innovative initiative that address crucial gap in medication safety by providing pharmacy personnel with fast, reliable access to drug information relevant to individuals with G6PD deficiency. Its practical design and intuitive interface offer a scalable tool that reduces the times and uncertainty of definite risk medications. Although still in the prototype stage, its early usability suggests strong potential for real world application. With continued refinement, validation studies and user feedback, G-MediAlert could evolve into a trusted reference resource across community pharmacies especially among locum pharmacists to support safer dispensing practice.

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